

DAHA SAMAKA DRAVYAS IN AYURVEDA: A REVIEW OF THERAPEUTIC AGENTS FOR BURNING SENSATION***¹Dr. Tanvi Sood, ²Dr. Deeksha Sharma, ³Dr. Udit Verma, ⁴Dr. Chandni Gupta*****¹Lecturer, ²PG Scholar, ³PG Scholar, ⁴Associate Professor,****PG Department of Dravyaguna, Rajiv Gandhi Government Post Graduate Ayurvedic College and Hospital Paprola, Teh. Baijnath, Kangra, Himachal Pradesh, India.**

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Corresponding Author*Dr. Tanvi Sood**

Lecturer, PG Department of
Dravyaguna, Rajiv Gandhi
Government Post Graduate Ayurvedic
College and Hospital Paprola, Teh.
Baijnath, Kangra, Himachal Pradesh,
India.

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda, the ancient Indian system of medicine, emphasizes balance among the three Doshas—Vata, Pitta, and Kapha—for maintaining health. Pitta, being associated with heat and metabolism, when aggravated, leads to various disorders, among which Daha (burning sensation) is prominent. Daha is classified as a Pittaja Nanatmaja Vyadhi, yet it can also occur as a symptom in multiple Pitta-related disorders such as Amlapitta (acid reflux), Mutrakrichra (urinary disorders), Twak Vikara (skin diseases), Jwara (fever), and Vrana (wounds). This literary review focuses on the classical Ayurvedic herbs known as Daha Śāmaka Dravyas—substances that alleviate burning sensations. These herbs are primarily found in Ayurvedic texts within various Ganas (herbal groups), characterized by specific properties such as Tikta (bitter), Kashaya (astringent), and Madhura (sweet) Rasa, Sheeta Veerya (cooling potency), Katu and Madhura Vipaka (post-digestive effect), and Guna like Laghu (light) and Ruksha (dry). These pharmacological

properties are central to their Pitta-pacifying actions. Through analysis of classical sources such as Charaka Samhita, the study identifies and categorizes several herbs traditionally employed to manage Daha. It further highlights the therapeutic roles these herbs play in disease-specific contexts, providing insight into their practical application. The consistent classical emphasis on Sheeta Veerya and Tikta Rasa in Daha Shamaka Dravyas underlines the Ayurvedic approach to cooling and balancing aggravated Pitta. This understanding forms

a basis for rational therapeutic usage of these herbs in contemporary practice, especially in managing conditions with dominant Pitta symptoms.

KEYWORDS: *Nana- Atamaja Roga, Daha, Daha- Prashamana, Herbs.*

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurvedic science, Daha refers to a pathological burning sensation occurring internally or externally in the body, commonly arising from an aggravation of Pitta Dosha. It may manifest in various regions such as the skin, gastrointestinal tract, chest, urinary system, or throughout the body, and may be associated with Vata and Rakta Dushti in certain cases. The substances that pacify this condition are termed Daha Prashamana Dravyas, which are specifically formulated to reduce heat and inflammation.

Traditionally, drugs possessing Sheeta (cool), Tikta (bitter), Madhura (sweet), and Snigdha (unctuous) properties have been indicated for their efficacy in relieving Daha. In contemporary times, due to the growing prevalence of Pitta-aggravating diets, lifestyles, and environmental toxins and metabolic imbalances, the relevance of these drugs has increased significantly. Furthermore, modern pharmacological studies support their anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, and hepatoprotective actions, reinforcing their applicability in both traditional and modern contexts.

OBJECTIVE

This review aims to critically examine classical references, pharmacological attributes, and therapeutic potentials of Daha Prashamana Dravyas, with a focus on their relevance in modern clinical practice.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The present review involves systematic tabulation and compilation of Daha-Prashamana (burning sensation-relieving) drugs based on classical Ayurvedic texts. The following steps were adopted in the methodology:

Primary Sources of Data Collection

Compilation of Daha-Prashamana Dravyas was conducted by referring to the following authoritative Ayurvedic texts:

Charaka Samhitā – Cikitsāsthāna and Sūtrasthāna (Gana section)

Suśruta Samhitā – Sūtrasthāna (Gana Samgraha)

Aṣṭāṅga Saṅgraha – Sūtrasthāna (Dravya classification)

Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya – Sūtrasthāna (Hṛdaya Gana and Dravya categorization)

Bhāvaprakāśa Nighaṅṭu

Pharmacological Properties Documented

Each Daha-Prashamana drug was evaluated and tabulated based on:

Rasa (Taste)

Vipāka (Post-digestive effect)

Vīrya (Potency)

Guṇa (Qualities)

Doṣa Karma (Effect on Tridoṣas: Vāta, Pitta, Kapha)

Secondary Sources & Textbooks

Dravyaguṇa Vijñāna textbooks by:

Prof. P.V. Sharma – Vol. I & II

Data Compilation and Analysis

A comparative table was created for selected Daha-Prashamana herbs.

Disease-wise indications from classical texts were compiled.

Inclusion Criteria

Only herbs that were specifically mentioned in relation to Daha, Pittaja Vyadhi, or possessing Śīta-Vīrya and Tikta/Madhura Rasa were included.

Exclusion Criteria

Formulations, mineral-origin substances (Rasa Dravyas), and complex polyherbal recipes were excluded for scope limitation.

RESULTS

Daha-Prashamana dravyas^[1-13](Table 1)

Sr.no	Name of Gana	C.S	Su. S	A. S	A.H
1.	<i>Dahaprashmana Gana</i>	+	-	+	-
2.	<i>Sarivadi Gana</i>	-	+	-	+
3.	<i>Anjanadi Gana</i>	-	+	-	+
4.	<i>Nygodhradi Gana</i>	-	+	-	+
5.	<i>Guduchyadi Gana</i>	-	+	-	+
6.	<i>Utpaladi Gana</i>	-	+	-	-
7.	<i>Pittanashaka Gana</i>	-	-	-	+

C. S: Charaka Samhita, Su.S: Sushrytha Samhita, A.S: Ashtanga Sangraha, A.H: Ashtanga Hrudaya.

Findings

Nyagrodhadi Gana is the most widely accepted group, mentioned in all four major classical texts.

Guduchyadi and Dahaprashamana Gana are mentioned only in Charaka and Ashtanga Sangraha respectively.

Pittanashaka Gana is referenced only in Ashtanga Sangraha and Ashtanga Hridaya, highlighting its later inclusion.

Sarivadi Gana, Anjamadi Gana, and Utpaladi Gana are primarily found in Sushruta Samhita, with some overlap in other texts.

This shows a diverse understanding of Daha-shamaka (burn-alleviating) formulations across texts, with different Acharyas emphasizing different groups based on clinical experience or regional herbal availability.

List of Daha Prashamana Dravya mentioned in classical literature;^[14] (Table 2)

Sanskrit name	Latin name	Part used
1. Lajja (Fried paddy or Fried unmilled rice)	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	Seeds
2. Chandana	<i>Santalum album</i> Linn.	Heartwood, oil
3. Kashmarya Phala	<i>Gmelina arborea</i> Linn.	Root,fruit
4. Madhuka	<i>Madhuca indica</i> J.F.Gmel	Flower, seed, oil
5. Usheera	<i>Vetiveria zizanioides</i> Linn.	Root
6. Sariva dvya	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> R.Br.	Root
7. Guduchi	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> Willd.	Kaand
8. Mulethi	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> Linn.	Root
9. Padmaka	<i>Prunus cerasoides</i> D.Don.	Tvak, beejmajja
10. Naagkesara	<i>Mesua ferrae</i> Linn.	Punkesar
11. Priyangu	<i>Callicarpa macrophylla</i> Vahl.	Flower
12. Nyagodhra	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> Linn.	Tvak, latex, leaves, paroha, fruit
13. Udumbara	<i>Ficus racemose</i> Roxb.	Tvak, fruit, ksheer, bark
14. Ashwatha	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> Linn	Bark, fruit, shung, latex
15. Plaksha	<i>Ficus lacor</i> Buch-Ham	Tvak
16. Kapitana	<i>Thespesia populnea</i> ex Correa	Tvak

17. <i>Kakubha</i>	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> Roxb	Tvak
18. <i>Aamra</i>	<i>Mangifera indica</i> Linn.	Bark, leaves, flower, fruit, beejmajja
19. <i>Koshaamra</i> (Bark)	<i>Schleichera oleosa</i> Lour	Tvak, seed, oil
20. <i>Chorak patra</i>	<i>Angelica glauca</i> Edgew.	Root
21. <i>Jambu dvya</i>	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> Linn	Fruit, phalasthi, tvak, patra
22. <i>Priyala</i>	<i>Buchanania lanzan</i> Spreng	Stem bark, Seed kernel
23. <i>Katurohini</i>	<i>Picrorhiza kurrooa</i> Royle. Ex Benth.	Rhizome
24. <i>Vetas</i>	<i>Salix caprea</i> Linn.	Bark, flower
25. <i>Kadamba</i>	<i>Anthocephalus cadamba</i> Miq	Tvak, fruit
26. <i>Badar</i>	<i>Ziziphus jujube</i> Mill.	Root, leaf, fruit
27. <i>Tinduka</i>	<i>Diospyros peregrina</i> Gaertn	Tvak, seed, fruit, seed oil
28. <i>Shallaki</i>	<i>Boswellia serrata</i> Roxb.	Tvak, Resin
29. <i>Lodhra</i> variety	<i>Symplocos racemose</i> Roxb.	Tvak
30. <i>Bhillawa</i>	<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i> Linn	Fruit
31. <i>Dhataki</i>	<i>Woodfordia fruticose</i> Kurz.	Flower
32. <i>Nimb</i>	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss	Flower, leaves, seed, oil, tvak
33. <i>Kustumbaru</i>	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i> Linn.	Fruit, oil, whole plant (fresh coriander)
34. <i>Utpala</i> varieties	<i>Nymphaea alba</i> Linn.	Roots, flower, seeds
35. <i>Vasa</i>	<i>Adhatoda vasica</i> Nees	Root, leaves, flower
36. <i>Aatamgupta</i>	<i>Mucuna prurita</i> Hook	Seeds, root, hairs
37. <i>Abhiru</i>	<i>Asparagus racemosa</i> Willd.	Rhizome
38. <i>Sheetpaki</i>	<i>Abrus prectorius</i> Linn.	Seed, root, leaves
39. <i>Shaalparni</i>	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> DC.	Whole plant
40. <i>Prishanparni</i>	<i>Uraria picta</i> Desv.	Root
41. <i>Vanya</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> Linn.	Rhizome

List of Rasa panchaka of Daha Prashamana Gana drugs^[15] (Table 3)

<i>Rasa</i>	No.	<i>Vipaka</i>	No.	<i>Veerya</i>	No.	<i>Guna</i>	No.	<i>Doshahara</i>	No.
<i>Kashaya</i>	29	<i>Katu</i>	25	<i>Sheeta</i>	31	<i>Laghu</i>	24	<i>Pitta</i>	39
<i>Tikta</i>	24	<i>Madhura</i>	16	<i>Ushna</i>	9	<i>Ruksha</i>	22	<i>Kapha</i>	34
<i>Madhura</i>	20	<i>Amla</i>	-	<i>Ishat Ushna</i>	1	<i>Guru</i>	16	<i>Vata</i>	16
<i>Katu</i>	4					<i>Snighdha</i>	12		
<i>Amla</i>	2					<i>Tikshana</i>	2		
<i>Lavana</i>	-					<i>Picchila</i>	1		
						<i>Sara</i>	1		

Numbers of drugs based on analysis of *Rasa*, *Vipaka*, *Veerya*, *Guna* and *Doshaharatwa*.

List of *Daha Prashamana* drugs (Disease wise) as per *Charaka Samhita*;^[16-44] (Table 4)

Jwara	Raktapitta	Gulma	Kushtha	Rajyakshma	Sotha	Pandu	Kasa	Madatyā	Vrana	Vatarakta
Ushir								Ushir		
Vanya										
Chandan	Chandan				Chandan	Chandan				Chandan
Prishniparni	Prishniparni			Prishniparni			Prishniparni			Prishniparni
Ashwatha										Ashwatha
Plaksha										
Kapitana										
Jambu										
Katurohini			Katurohini			Katurohini				
Kashmarya phala										
Sariva										
Mulethi		Mulethi	Mulethi		Mulethi				Mulethi	Mulethi,
Padmaka										Padmaka
Naagkesar								Naagkesar		
Priyangu	Priyangu							Priyangu		
Nyagrodh										
Udumbar										Udumbar
Kadamba										
Badar								Badar		
Dhatki										
Utpala bheda	Utpala bheda							Utpala bheda		
Vasa										
Abhiru							Abhiru			Abhiru
	Lodhra									
			Nimba			Nimba		Nimba		
								Guduchi		Guduchi
										Madhuka
										Kushumbhu
										Vetas

On all observations its found that *Charaka* has given single *Gana* of 10 drugs i.e *Daha-Prashamana Gana*, while *Sushruta* have mentioned 5 *Ganas* and *Vagbhata* have described 5 *Gana* in *Ashtanga Hrudya* and 1 *Gana* in *Ashtanga Sangraha*. *Nyagrodhadi Gana* is the most widely accepted group, mentioned in all four major classical texts. A total of 61 Drugs have been mentioned in these various groups [Table 1]. Analysis of 41 drugs has been made, which are taken from different *Ganas* of classical texts after excluding the controversial drugs [Table 2]. *Rasa* of drugs has been recorded. *Kashaya Rasa* is seen in 29 herbs, *Tikta Rasa* in 24, *Madhura Rasa* in 20, *Katu Rasa* in 4 and *Amla Rasa* in two herbs [Table 3]. In particular, a disease wise listing of *dahaprashmana* drugs mentioned in *Charak samhita* was developed to identified their relevace across different clinical conditions [Table 4].

सारांश

आयुर्वेद, जो कि भारत की प्राचीन चिकित्सा प्रणाली है, स्वास्थ्य की रक्षा के लिए वात, पित्त और कफ — इन तीनों दोषों के संतुलन पर बल देता है। पित्त दोष, जो गर्मी और चयापचय (metabolism) से

संबंधित होता है, जब विकृत होता है, तो अनेक रोग उत्पन्न होते हैं, जिनमें दाह (जलन) प्रमुख है। दाह को पित्तज नानात्मज व्याधि के रूप में वर्णित किया गया है, लेकिन यह आम्लपित्त, मूत्रकृच्छ्र, त्वक विकार, ज्वर और व्रण जैसे कई पित्तप्रधान विकारों के लक्षण के रूप में भी प्रकट हो सकता है। यह साहित्यिक समीक्षा दाह शामक द्रव्यों — अर्थात् जलन को शांत करने वाली औषधियों — पर केंद्रित है, जिनका उल्लेख आयुर्वेदिक ग्रंथों में विभिन्न गणों (हर्बल समूहों) में किया गया है। इन द्रव्यों की प्रमुख विशेषताएं तिक्त, कषाय और मधुर रस; शीत वीर्य; कटु व मधुर विपाक; तथा लघु और रूक्ष गुण होते हैं। ये सभी गुण पित्त को शमन करने में सहायक माने गए हैं। चरक संहिता जैसे प्राचीन ग्रंथों के आधार पर इस अध्ययन में दाह निवारण में प्रयुक्त अनेक औषधियों की पहचान और वर्गीकरण किया गया है। इसके साथ ही विभिन्न व्याधियों में इन द्रव्यों की चिकित्सीय भूमिका को स्पष्ट किया गया है। दाह शमन में शीत वीर्य और तिक्त रस के महत्त्व पर आयुर्वेदिक शास्त्रों में विशेष बल दिया गया है। यह ज्ञान वर्तमान चिकित्सा पद्धति में पित्तप्रधान लक्षणों वाले रोगों के प्रबंधन हेतु इन औषधियों के युक्तियुक्त उपयोग का मार्ग प्रशस्त करता है।

DISCUSSION

Analysis of the herbs clearly indicates that *Kashaya Rasa Dravyas* dominates the list (29) followed by *Tikta* (24), *Madhura* (19), *Katu* (4), *Amla* (2) *Rasa* drugs [table 3]. Maximum herbs are with *Kashaya*, *Tikta* and *Madhura Rasas*. These three *rasas* are *Pitta* pacifying *Rasas* and also in *Charaka Sutra Sthana* 26-chapter *Rasa's Guna-Karma* has been described and clearly indicate *Madhura* and *Tikta Rasa* having *Daha Prashamana Karma*. Also, these 3 *Rasas* have *Sheeta Guna* which helps in *Daha Prashamana*.

Dravya and *guna* both have a *Samavayi* relationship in which *Guna* reside in *Dravyas* and have a second place to it. *Daha Prashamana* herbs can achieve the therapeutic effect by the dominance of *Gunas* like *Laghu* (Light), *Ruksha* (Dry), *Guru* (Heavy), *Snigdha* (oily). It is also observed some of drugs have *Tikshana* (2), *Picchila* (1) and *Sara* (1) *Guna*. *Laghu Guna* is associated with *Madhura Rasa*, *Madhura Vipaka* and *Katu Vipaka* which facilitates for detoxification of *Pitta*. *Daha Prashamana* drugs have these *gunas* in combinations. So may be the presence of *Jala Mahabhuta*, *pitta-shamaka* property helps in pacifying the *Daha*. 31 herbs have *Sheeta Virya* that directly helps in pacifying *Daha*.

Sushruta's classification of *Vipaka* reflects two dominant *Gunas* i.e *Guru* and *Laghu* further quoted as *Katu* and *Madhura Vipaka*. Drugs with *Katu Vipaka* (25) are relatively more in number followed by *madhura* (16 herbs). *Daha Prashamana* herbs have both *Katu* and *Madhura Vipaka* helps in pacifying *Pitta* Symptoms and *Daha* is one of them.

Majority of herbs possessing *pittahara* (39 herbs) and *Kaphhara*(34 herbs) activity. Out of 41 herbs under observation 39 drugs have *Pittahara* activity, which usually employed to treat *Daha*.

Acharaya Charaka has mentioned only one *gana* for *Daha Prashamana* herbs (Anti-burning syndrome drugs or refrigerants). *Acharya Sushruta* in *Sushruta Samhita* and *Vagbhata* in *Ashtanga Hrudya* has given 5 *ganas* to be *Daha Prashamana*. *Utpaladi Gana* is mentioned as *Daha Prashamana* by *sushruta* but not mentioned in *Ashtanga Hrudya*. In spite of *Utpaladi Gana*, *Pittashamaka Gana* is mentioned in *Ashtanga Hrudya*. In *Ashtanga Sangraha* only *Daha Prashamana Gana* is mentioned like *Charaka Samhita* but in spite of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia*), *Padmaka* (*Prunus cerasoides*) is mentioned. *Guduchi* is the only drug in *Daha Prashamana Mahakshaya* mentioned in *Charaka Samhita* which has *Ushna Veerya* (hot potency) that's why may be *Vagbhata* replaced it with *Padmaka* having *Sheeta Veerya*(cold Potency).

Out of 41 drugs 20 drugs are mentioned by *Acharya Charaka* for *Jwar vyadhi*, 5 for *Raktpitta*, 1 for *Gulma*, 3 for *Kushtha*, 1 for *Rajyakshma*, 2 for *Sotha*, 3 for *Pandu*, 2 for *Kasa*, 7 for *Madatyay*, 1 for *Vrana*, 11 for *Vatarakta*.

CONCLUSION

This review critically examined the classical references, pharmacological attributes, and therapeutic relevance of *Daha-Prashamana Dravyas* as found in *Ayurvedic literature*. The analysis of various *Ganas* reveals that these drug groups possess a broad spectrum of pharmacological properties that are effective in managing *Daha*, a burning sensation predominantly seen in *Paittika* disorders. Group of drugs i.e *Ganas* mentioned in *Ayurvedic literatures* have multiple pharmacological properties. On observation we come to know how different herbs acted on *Daha* with different properties. this observation is useful for designing new formulations to treat *Daha* or *Daha* associated as a symptom in *Paittika* disorder. Drugs that are *Kashaya*, *Tikta*, *Madhura* in *Rasa*, possessing *Sheeta Virya* and having *Laghu*, *Ruksha*, *Snigdha*, *Guru Guna* are largely responsible for *Daha Prashamanan*.

The Disease-wise review of *Daha-Prashaman* drugs (table 4) of *Charaka Samhita* shows the predominance of *Pitta Doshas* in all the diseases and these drugs possess *Pittashamaka* property. The holistic approach using Rasa, Guna, Vipaka, and Karma not only helps in symptomatic relief but also addresses the underlying Dosha imbalance, making the Ayurvedic approach rational, systematic, and therapeutically effective.

Burning sensation is a type of pain that's distinct from dull, stabbing, or aching pain. Today many conditions are there like Rosacea, GERD, PVDs, Neuralgia, Megaloblastic anaemia etc that cause a burning sensation and have no permanent cure in allopathy. In this regard, an attempt had been made to literally review the *Daha-Prashamana* Drugs (herbs) mentioned in *Ganas* (group of drugs) of *Ayurvedic* classical texts which can make a big difference in treating burning sensation in different diseases.

Furthermore, this study opens avenues for future research—including pharmacological validation, clinical trials, and formulation development—based on the principles of Ayurveda. Exploring these herbs through modern scientific tools can bridge traditional wisdom with contemporary evidence-based medicine, enhancing their utility in modern healthcare.

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